

POSTBUCKLING FAILURE OF A BLADE-STIFFENED CARBON-EPOXY COMPRESSION PANEL

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SUMMARY: The failure of postbuckled panels with blade-stiffeners has been studied experimentally. A new failure mechanism was identified for this particular type of stiffener where failure is initiated by a critical shear stress in the web. This shear stress was calculated from strain gauge measurements using lamination theory and incorporating edge effects. The critical shear stress was found to agree with the shear strength obtained from a three-point bending test of the web laminate.

KEYWORDS: buckling, postbuckling, failure, stiffened carbon-epoxy panel, axial compression.

INTRODUCTION

The failure of a postbuckled carbon-epoxy compression panel is invariably explosive and results in the complete destruction of the panel. However, the failure mechanism is initiated locally at a point in the panel corresponding to either a nodal [1,2,3] or an anti-nodal line [4,5] of the buckling mode. At these locations the deformations and stress resultants have maximum values.

A program of experimental work in the Aeronautics Department at Imperial College was undertaken to investigate the postbuckling failure of a number of carbon-fibre composite compression panels with different stiffener configurations [4,5,6]. This work was motivated by the well known observation that the failure load of such structures may exceed the buckling load by a factor of two or more. For this reserve of postbuckled strength to be accessible to the designer, the failure load must be amenable to calculation. That is, the failure mechanism must be understood.

Previous work [4,5] has identified failure initiation mechanisms for panels which have I or J stiffeners, shown in Fig. 1.1(a) and Fig. 1.1(b). These stiffeners were characterised by their relatively high torsional stiffness arising from the torsion/bending stiffness of the stiffener caps. At the anti-nodal lines in I and J stiffened panels, the buckle deformations gave rise to a moment in the stiffener which tended to pull the stiffener from the skin. The failure of each of these panel types was shown to be a consequence of the separation of the stiffeners from the skin, initiated at an anti-nodal line and starting from a local stress concentration such as the edge of the stiffener

flange or at the base of the stiffener web. The blade stiffeners of the panel design investigated in this paper have only low St. Venant torsional stiffness and no torsional/bending component. Thus the loading action which destroyed the I and J stiffened panels could not develop and a different failure initiation mechanism was expected, and indeed found, away from the stiffener base stress concentrations. This paper describes the test-panels and the strain gauge placement used to determine the relevant stress resultants at failure. A fractographic survey of the failure mechanism indicated a shear failure in the stiffener web. The stress resultants were used to calculate the magnitude of the critical shear stress from lamination theory. This critical shear stress was then compared with the value obtained from a three-point bending test of the web laminate.

In [4,6] the test of a component representing a small section of the test panel but exhibiting a similar failure mechanism has proved instructive. In this paper a component consisting of a length of blade stiffener and panel skin (tested in compression) was shown to exhibit an identical failure mode to the panel.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

Test Panels

The details of the blade-stiffened panel design are shown in Fig. 1(c) and Fig. 2. Two panels were manufactured from unidirectional prepreg T800/924C and the stiffeners were secondary bonded to the skin using a film adhesive. In forming the taper in the flanges, the outer 90/0/90 plies form a protective envelope against the initiation of interply cracking due to the transverse bending which occurs in the postbuckled panel at anti-nodal locations [4].

The panel ends were potted in an epoxy resin/fibre glass mixture and machined parallel to ensure uniform loading. The two panels tested were loaded in uniaxial compression in a custom built hyperstiff 250 ton testing machine under displacement control so that catastrophic failure in compression could be assessed. The unloaded edges were unsupported.

Panel Instrumentation

Fig. 2 shows the strain gauges initially applied to the second panel tested. As will be discussed in a later section dealing with the failure mode, the initiation of failure in the first panel was seen to occur in the stiffener web at mid-span, i.e., corresponding to a nodal-line of the buckled mode. At the node line, the twisting moment in the stiffener is a maximum and the transverse shear force in the web due to the compression loading is also a maximum. The strain gauges are thus positioned to capture the shear strain and the distribution of compression strain in the web. From these measurements the shear stress in the web at failure can be calculated, using an approximate analysis, and compared with an experimental value obtained from a three-point bending test of the web laminate.

It will be seen (Figs. 4 & 7) that the second panel tested exhibited a mode switch from four half-wavelengths to five half-wavelengths just before failure. This necessitated unloading the panel and mounting more strain gauges *in-situ* at the new nodal-line locations prior to the final test to failure.

Figure 1 : (a) I-Stiffener (b) J-Stiffener
(c) Half-Section of Blade-Stiffened Panel.

Figure 2 : Strain Gauge Locations.

INITIAL BUCKLING

An in-house finite element package, FE77 [7], was used for the linear numerical analysis presented in this paper. Fig. 3 shows the first buckling mode shape, of four half-wavelengths, predicted to occur at a load of 113.84 kN using a linear eigenvalue finite element analysis. This agreed well with the experimentally recorded value of 110 kN for the first panel and 105 kN for the second panel. The critical load associated with the second eigenvalue, corresponding to a five half-wavelength mode shape, was calculated at 115.96 kN. The close proximity of these two modes help to explain the mode switch observed in the second panel. Fig. 4 is a shadow Moiré fringe pattern of the second panel soon after buckling has occurred. Because the width between the central stiffeners is double that between the edge stiffeners, the buckle deformations develop earlier in the central region. Fig. 5 shows the strains measured by back-to-back gauges on the skin in the central bay. The buckling is well defined and there is no detectable bending deformation prior to the bifurcation of the strains.

Figure 3 : First Buckling Mode Shape from an Eigenvalue Analysis (Load = 113.84 kN).

Figure 4 : Shadow Moiré Fringe Pattern of Buckled Panel.

Postbuckling Characteristics

During the test of the first panel, since the site of failure initiation was then unknown, it was considered relevant to monitor the transverse bending strain in the skin adjacent to the stiffener flange at an anti-nodal line. This is where bending is a maximum and where the flange peeling described in Ref. 1 would occur. In Fig. 6(a) it is noted that the bending strain reverses sign at a load of approximately 250 kN. This is because of the rotation of the stiffener due to its reduced torsional stiffness under the increased compression, illustrated in Fig. 6(b). Although this may be considered to be a mode change, it occurs gradually and doesn't have the dynamic characteristics of the mode switch which has been observed in other experimental work on postbuckled panels [3,4] and the second panel tested. Apart from this, the deformations and strains in the first panel increased monotonically until the explosive failure described in the next section.

In testing the second panel, use was made of the observations on the first. The strain gauges were placed at nodal lines as shown in Fig. 2. However at a load of 570 kN a dynamic mode switch was observed and the new mode shape of five half-wavelengths is shown in Figure 7. To investigate nodal-line strain values at failure required a repositioning of the strain gauges at the new node lines. The relocated gauge numbers were identified by the suffix **B** and these were placed at corresponding locations on the new node line.

Fig. 8 shows the output from back-to-back strain gauges 9 and 12. Initially these gauges were near a nodal-line so that the bending strain (the strain difference) is small. When the mode switch occurs we see that a large bending strain was induced thus indicating that this location no longer corresponded to a nodal-line. The data shown in Fig. 8 was recorded on the final test to failure (in all, four loading cycles were conducted to various load levels [8]) when the mode switch was seen to occur at a load of 548 kN.

Figure 5 : Back-to-Back Strain Gauges 2 and 20.

Figure 6 : (a) *Transverse Bending Strain* (b) *Deformed Cross-Section.*

The Failure Mode

The first panel failed explosively at a load of 573 kN. The failed panel is shown in Fig. 9 where it is seen that the damage in each stiffener occurred at mid-span, i.e. at a nodal-line in the buckled mode. Closer inspection revealed that at these locations there was mid-plane delamination initiating at the free edge of the stiffener web. The failure of the second panel, which underwent a mode switch to five half-wavelengths at 548 kN, occurred at 601 kN and the characteristic web delamination was again observed at the nodal-lines. In this case, the failure across the left-hand stiffeners occurred at the node-line below the mid-span and at the node-line above mid-span for the right-hand stiffeners.

In these panel failures the stiffeners, for the most part, remained attached to the skin. This is in contrast to the failure of I and J stiffened panels where the failure initiation was at a skin/stiffener interface [4,5] and stiffener debonding at collapse was extensive.

Figure 7 : *Shadow Moiré Fringe Pattern of Postbuckled Panel Showing a Mode-Switch to Five Half-Wavelengths.*

Figure 8 : Back-to-Back Strain Gauges 9 and 12.

Figure 9 : Failed First Panel.

CALCULATION OF FAILURE STRESS

The stress resultants acting on an element of the stiffener web are shown in Fig. 10. Observations from the experiments suggest that a critical value of interlaminar shear stress τ_{xz} was reached in the mid-plane of the web, at the free edge and on a nodal-line. There are two contributions to this shear stress which come from the transverse shear loading N_{xz} and the twisting moment M_{xy} . Both these stress resultants have maximum values at a nodal-line.

Mid-Plane Shear Stress τ_{xz} due to N_{xz}

From a measurement of the surface direct strains at the nodal-line, the web compressive loading N_{xx} can be calculated, knowing the laminate properties. Also, if the surface shear strains are measured, the laminate rate of twist can be found and hence the transverse shear force per unit length at the free edge, N_{xz} . Lamination theory then gives us the mid-plane shear stress τ_{xz} . By letting w refer to the displacement in the z -direction, the transverse shear force per unit length is given by:

$$N_{xz} = N_{xx} \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 11 shows the measured shear strain on two surfaces at a node-line. Notice the sudden increase in shear strain at the mode switch and the slight drop in load. The mid-plane shear stress at failure due to N_{xz} was calculated to be:

$$\tau_{xz(1)} = 37.2 \text{ MPa} \quad (2)$$

Figure 10 : Failure Mechanism.

Mid-Plane Shear Stress τ_{xz} due to M_{xy}

In Ref. 9 the extent of edge effects in a composite laminate under pure torsion was assessed. Here the in-plane shear stresses, τ_{xy} , which react the torque in the centre of the section, go to zero at the free edge resulting in a sympathetic rise in the interlaminar shear stress, τ_{xz} . As seen from the free edge, these stresses decay exponentially over a distance which is a function of the ratio of the in-plane effective shear modulus, G_{xy} and the transverse shear modulus G_{xz} . It can be shown [9] that at the free edge and at the midplane of the laminate thickness, τ_{xz} , may be expressed as:

$$\tau_{xz} = \alpha \sum \tau_{xy(k)}^0 \cdot \Delta t \quad (3)$$

where Δt is the ply thickness, $\tau_{xy(k)}^0$ is the shear stress in ply k , as calculated by lamination theory, i.e., away from the edge, and the summation is taken from the surface to the mid-plane of the laminate. The coefficient α is given by:

$$\alpha^2 = \frac{12G_{xz}}{t^2 G_{xy}} \quad (4)$$

The mid plane interlaminar shear stress at failure due to M_{xy} has been calculated to be

$$\tau_{xz(2)} = 42.0 \text{ MPa} \quad (5)$$

Thus the total mid-plane shear stress at the free edge of the stiffener web at a nodal-line and at the failure load is the sum of $\tau_{xz(1)}$ and $\tau_{xz(2)}$:

$$\tau_{xz(\text{total})} = \tau_{xz(1)} + \tau_{xz(2)} = 79.2 \text{ MPa} \quad (6)$$

Interlaminar Shear Strength

The interlaminar shear strength of the web laminate was determined by a three-point bending test on a web section of the stiffener. At failure, the mid-plane shear stress, τ_{xz} , was calculated to be 77.0 MPa. This result agreed well with the value obtained from the above analysis and provides supporting evidence to the proposed failure mechanism.

Figure 11 : Shear Strain at the Higher Mode Nodal-Line of the Stiffener Web.

Figure 12 : Test Component.

COMPONENT TEST

In previous investigations into the mechanisms leading to the failure of stiffened panels [4,6], a separate test of a small section of the panel, under representative loads or deformations, was undertaken to provide further insight into the initiation of failure. The component in this case was a length of stiffener and its associated skin, as shown in Fig. 12, loaded in uniaxial compression. The length was chosen so that the wavelength of torsional buckling was similar to the wavelength observed in the panel. The failure of the component was identical, i.e., a mid-plane delamination of the stiffener web at a nodal-line. Although the compressive loading was not the same as in the panel, the combination of compression and twist produced a similar total mid-plane shear stress.

CONCLUSION

The failure of a postbuckled panel with unflanged stiffeners may initiate in the free edge boundary layer of the stiffener web. This is in contrast with the other panels tested at the Department of Aeronautics in Imperial College where stiffener debonding usually preceded collapse. Experimental investigation of postbuckling failure has proved to be indispensable in gaining an understanding of failure mechanisms. In practice such an understanding is a *sine qua non* for the finite element modeller. Non-linear finite element modelling incorporating a global-local procedure for failure analysis will be reported in a paper which is in preparation.

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